

CORPORATE MANAGEMENT: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND ORGANIZATIONAL ECONOMIC ASPECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15121292>

Abstract. *This article describes the theoretical and methodological aspects of corporate management in financial relations. A classification of principles of corporate governance in financial relations is presented. Also, the factors affecting the effectiveness of corporate management in financial relations are identified and their essence is revealed. On the basis of the results of the research, proposals and recommendations have been developed on the effective establishment of corporate management of financial relations in corporate structures.*

Keywords: *corporate governance, corporate structure, joint stock company, investment attractiveness, investment climate, financial relations, investors, shareholders, business ethics, manager, corporation.*

Introduction. In the experience of developed countries in the world, the main attention is paid to the reasons of corporate management in ensuring the financial stability of large joint-stock companies, corporations and structures. In this regard, each structure that engages in financial relations tries to achieve financial efficiency through corporate management, giving priority to the activities of certain structures in its activities. Also, “increasing the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies, the priority and urgency of ensuring high rates of growth of the national economy by attracting foreign strategic investors has led to increased attention to the quality and efficiency of corporate management [1]”.

In Uzbekistan, it is important to develop the activities of joint-stock companies, commercial organizations, and economic entities based on modern trends, to ensure the effectiveness of their financial activities, to introduce and develop the principles of corporate governance. Development of economic and financial activities of the Republic, modernization of corporate management activities in order to make wide use of the experiences of developed countries in increasing the attractiveness of the investment environment, and implementation of international standards in the diversification of its financial and institutional structure have gained priority. In this direction, the financial relations and corporate management system of large commercial banks, which are joint-stock companies and financial service institutions operating in our country, require efforts to be made in accordance with international standards in terms of form and content. A number of normative and legal documents are being adopted, which led to the acceleration of important reforms in the field: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 24, 2015 No. PF-4720 "On measures to introduce modern corporate management methods in joint-stock companies [2] ", PQ-2635 dated 17.10.2016 "On measures to further improve corporate governance in joint-stock companies where the state share is the priority [3] " In the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated 29.11.2022 No. 679 "On approval of the administrative regulation of the provision of state services on the issuance of the certificate of

qualification of a corporate manager [5] ", importance is attached to modern international standards of corporate management in financial relations, the wide introduction of their requirements and methods.

Taking into account the above, it is of urgent importance to introduce the principles of corporate management in financial relations, to evaluate their effectiveness and to ensure the priority of corporate etiquette in the relations between the participants of financial relations. In this regard, it is appropriate to research the scientific-theoretical foundations of the organization of corporate governance in financial relations. In this regard, the results of the scientific research activities of foreign and CIS economic scientists and our republic will be considered.

Literature review. Z.A.Ashurov's scientific research on the "concept and essence of corporate management [5]" describes the emergence of the concept of corporate management in financial relations and the evolutionary processes in this regard:

The term "corporate governance" itself historically originated in the mid-1970s in the United States. Later, this term spread widely in Europe, where researches in the fields of corporate management, corporate law and creation of corporate structures (organizations) continued [6]. As a result of research, it became clear that the term "corporate management" was first coined by R.Eells [7] to reveal the essence of "the structure and functioning of the corporate system". The concept of "corporate governance" itself has been known for a long time, and this concept was used in the literature published at the beginning of the 20th century. In particular, the system of corporate relations as a process of applying the management of corporate and private property was first introduced in 1932 by the American legal scholar A. Burley and economist G. Studied in the classic works of G.Minz [8]. Although the term "corporate governance" was not mentioned in their work, they studied the agency relationship between corporate governance trustees (outsiders, investors) and representatives (insiders, managers). "From a financial point of view: according to Z.A. Ashurov, corporate management is a single decision to ensure the return of the capital providers (investors, shareholders) invested in the corporation and to control the rational use and fair distribution of the corporation's financial resources, taking into account their interests. means of arrival [9].

According to the scientific research on "The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial leverage-profitability relationship: Evidence from Vietnam" conducted by Hanh Song Thi Pham and Duy Thanh Nguyen, "corporate governance is a collective structure of economic activities and capital is a holistic mechanism that ensures the growth of value. In this, the main attention should be paid to the proper organization of financial relations between major shareholders and minority shareholders [10].

In the scientific research of economists such as Shoyb Rostamia, Zeynab Rostamib, Samin Kohansal on the topic "The Effect of Corporate Governance Components on Return on Assets and Stock Return of Companies Listed in Tehran Stock Exchange", the following is especially noted: "Today, the success of large companies, corporations' importance and role of corporate governance in financial relations. The reason is that due to recent world financial instabilities, tension and financial crisis of companies, this issue is becoming more and more urgent all over the world. Research has shown that the issue of corporate governance in financial relations in Iran, its current concept was proposed in 2002. According to him, first of all, ownership cannot be meaningfully separated from corporate management [11].

According to Rizky Fadhillah¹ and Dian Imanina Burhany, scientists of the Institute of Corporate Governance of Indonesia, "in the implementation of financial relations, corporate governance is manifested as a process, structure and mechanism used in the management of the company. The main purpose of its application is to increase the value of shares in the long-term perspective, while paying sufficient attention to the interests of other interested parties. According to the classical theory of corporate governance, it is a means of convincing investors that they will get back what they have invested. Financial indicators are important in corporate management, which is a description of the financial conditions that can be a criterion for the success of the company. It can also be said that corporate governance is interconnected with corporate value. Because changes in financial indicators affect the value of the company. Financial performance can mediate corporate governance on corporate value [12]."

Analysis and results. Bob Tricker approached the theory of corporate governance based on the following aspects:

Picture 1. The concept of corporate governance Bob Tricker approaches [13]

According to research conducted by Pham, Hanh and Nguyen, Duy Thanh on "The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial leverage–profitability relationship", "First, corporate governance mechanisms in financial relations play a beneficial role in increasing the efficiency of debt use. Measures in this area determine the impact of financial leverage on corporate governance through various factors. Second, our research suggests that not accounting for corporate governance factors may lead to inconsistent results of the financial leverage–firm performance relationship. In this regard, despite numerous studies on the impact of debt capital financing on firm performance, the results remain inconclusive. In studying the relationship between financial leverage and performance, influencing factors should be considered. The main

conclusion from our research is that corporate governance mechanisms in financial relations affect the effectiveness of financial leverage [10].

Based on the results of a scientific study conducted by Ludo Horsthuis, a researcher at the University of Twente in the Netherlands, on the topic "Internal corporate governance mechanisms and corporate performance: evidence from Dutch listed firms", "Corporate governance", which ensures the effectiveness of financial relations, simultaneously includes finance, accounting, entrepreneurial law, business includes several organizational functions such as ethics and economics. It is also relevant to other corporate aspects such as reporting, transparency, disclosure, social responsibility, fairness and relations between the board of directors, shareholders and stakeholders [14]". In the scientific research conducted by the researcher, financial relations in corporate management are mainly organized on the basis of two models, including:

- Anglo-Saxon model;
- continental European model.

The above-mentioned models of corporate governance in financial relations differ from each other in several respects. Although national models in some developing countries are largely derived from these two models, it should also be noted that some country-specific adjustments have been made:

- "Anglo-Saxon model" is the US and UK corporate governance system of financial relations. In this model, the main responsibility of corporate managers is to maximize shareholder returns. This is because they have assumed the risks as owners of the company. Under the model, a joint-stock company is governed by a board of directors, which is usually single-tier and mainly consists of non-executive directors elected by the shareholders. The model is characterized by mutual financial relations between corporations (boards) and investors (shareholders).

- the "continental European model" is mainly used in European countries: the Netherlands, Germany, France, where European citizenship law applies. This model differs from the Anglo-Saxon model in several ways. In particular, the continental European model used in the corporate governance of financial relations focuses more on the stakeholder theory and mainly focuses on the returns of internal and external parties. Nevertheless, under this model, shareholders still have great power. Also, the investment activity is significant due to the contribution of commercial banks.

According to the Russian economist-scientist A. Baronov, "Corporate management" in financial relations is a system of financial relations characterized by specific structures and processes. For example, the financial relationship between shareholders and managers is that the former provides capital to the latter in order to earn a return on their investment. Managers, in turn, are required to provide shareholders with transparent financial information and reports on the company's activities on a regular basis. Shareholders also elect a supervisory body (usually a board of directors or a supervisory board) to represent their interests. This body, in fact, provides strategic direction and supervises the company's managers. Managers report to the supervisory body, which in turn reports to shareholders (through a general meeting of shareholders). The structures and processes that define these relationships are usually associated with various performance management, control and accounting mechanisms [15].

In addition to the above, a number of other definitions of corporate governance can be given:

- the system that manages and controls business organizations [17];

- an organizational model in which the company represents and protects the interests of its shareholders [18];

- the system of management and control of financial activity of the enterprise [19].

According to the methodology of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), we see that the principles of "corporate governance" in financial relations are expressed as follows:

Picture 3. Principles of corporate governance in financial relations [20]

According to the system of principles of corporate governance in financial relations:

- the principle of justice. The corporate governance system must protect the rights of shareholders and ensure equal treatment of all shareholders, including minority and foreign shareholders. All shareholders should have effective remedies in case of violation of their rights;

- the principle of responsibility. The corporate governance system should recognize the legal rights of stakeholders and facilitate the development of active cooperation between joint stock companies and stakeholders to ensure the sustainability of wealth, jobs and financially stable enterprises;

- the principle of transparency. The corporate governance system should ensure timely disclosure of reliable information about all important issues related to the joint-stock company, including its financial status, results of operations, ownership and management structure;

- the principle of accountability. The corporate governance system should ensure strategic management of the company, effective control over managers by the board of directors, as well as accountability of the board of directors to the company and its shareholders [17].

Yu.M. Chebotar's monograph entitled "Corporate Management" provides a comparative analysis of the definitions of the term "Corporate Management":

Table 1

Definitions of the term "corporate governance [21]"

№	Definitions	Economists
1	Corporate governance is the continuous, consistent provision of corporate interests, which is manifested in corporate control relations.	E.P. Gubin
2	Corporate governance is a set of influences on the process of managing and controlling the activities of corporations.	I.S. Shitkina
3	The process of development, acceptance and implementation of the decision made by the management bodies of the business entity should be understood as the process of corporate management of the business entity.	A.A. Serebryakova

Based on the above, Yu.M.Chebotar emphasized that "corporate management" in financial relations is the systematic management of a corporation, and it is noted that it includes the following:

- the priority of owners' interests and their role in the development of the corporation;
- organizational-legal registration and regulation of business activities (including optimization of business structures and business divisions of the business entity), establishing internal and external relations of the enterprise based on the goals set for itself;
- development and implementation of the corporation's mission and long-term development strategy;
- consideration of corporate relations (interactions between the owners of the corporation);
- formation and operation of corporate culture, including relevant traditions, attitudes, principles of behavior [22].

According to professor M.B. Khamidulin, "corporate management is a conscious and real influence of the owners of the corporation on the determination and adoption of strategic decisions aimed at the formation of the capital of the corporation, its more effective use for the purpose of profit, and the fair distribution of the received income among all participants of corporate relations, direct participation" [23].

According to the opinions of D. Suyunov and E. Khoshimov, who conducted a number of scientific studies on the methodological aspects of evaluating [24] the effectiveness of corporate management in joint-stock companies, "In most CIS countries, in particular, in the Russian Federation and Kazakhstan, the candidate's work activity (in the company, its subsidiaries and affiliated enterprises) is used to determine the status of an independent director) period is defined as the last three years. In Uzbekistan, setting this standard at five years will further limit the number of candidates for independent membership [1]. According to Z.Karimov, the efficiency methodology of "corporate management" should serve not only management efficiency, but also production efficiency. Today, the following factors influence the effectiveness of corporate management:

Picture 4. Factors affecting the effectiveness of corporate management in financial relations [25]

According to the interpretation of D.Kh.Suyunov and B.R.Tursunov, "corporate management is a set of laws and regulations based on and regulated by the management of companies' activities. It includes internal and external factors that affect the interests of the company's shareholders, as well as customers, suppliers, and management bodies. Thus, the corporation controls itself, setting its own values, policies, and laws for employees from the highest to the lowest levels. Good corporate governance seeks to ensure that all shareholders have the right to vote at general meetings. In this case, all shareholders should have the same idea about the future of the company [26].

Analyzing the scientific-theoretical aspects discussed above, corporate management theories can be classified as follows:

Based on the above, it can be said that corporate governance - it is a set of rules aimed at the proper management of the company, where it is important to divide the main tasks. Many definitions in the scientific literature summarize this concept as healthy management in an expanded interpretation. However, balancing the interests of the parties participating in the enterprise's activities is an important aspect of corporate governance.

Conclusions. It should be noted that corporate structures have a centralized pyramidal structure, two classic classifications of shares, pre-dividend "agreements" between shareholders, and other various means of controlling shareholders, such as mutual shareholding, regardless of which model of corporate governance is being used in Europe, the United States, as well as Widespread in Asia, of course. In corporate management in all developed countries, there are tendencies to increase the importance of the board of directors, to limit the functions of the chief executive and chairman of the board in corporate structures by including independent directors in the board of directors.

In general, there will be an opportunity to improve the effectiveness of corporate governance relations by integrating the best foreign practices of corporate governance into the national governance system.

Based on the reviewed advanced foreign experiences, we believe that the implementation of the following will have a positive effect in order to further increase the efficiency of corporate management in Uzbekistan:

- based on the Anglo-American model, corporate structures were issued to the stock market in the amount of authorized capital

Public placement of 70-80 percent of securities on the "Tashkent" republican stock exchange;

- to further liberalize the financial relations of corporate structures in legal terms by integrating the national legislative documents regulating the financial relations of corporate structures with advanced foreign experiences;

- in order to further develop the tax management within the financial relations in corporate structures, it is appropriate to include the tax consultant institute in the management structure of each corporate structure.

Picture 5. Groups of theories on corporate management [Classified by the author based on research]

REFERENCES

1. Suyunov D., Hoshimov E. Methodological aspects of evaluating the effectiveness of corporate management in joint-stock companies. Scientific electronic magazine "Economy and innovative technologies". No. 2, March-April, 2018
2. <https://lex.uz/docs/2635197>
3. <https://lex.uz/docs/3099256>
4. <https://lex.uz/docs/6300099>
5. http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz/sites/default/files/maqolalar/33_Z_Ashurov.pdf
6. Veasey E.N. The Emergence of Corporate Governance as a New Legal Discipline // The Business Lawyer. – August 1993. – Vol.48, Issue 4. - P.1267-1271.
7. Eells R.S.F. The Meaning of Modern Business: An Introduction to the Philosophy of Large Corporate Enterprise. – New York: Columbia University Press, 1960. – 427 p
8. Berle A., Means G. The modern Corporation and Private Property – New York: Macmillan, 1932. – 478 p.
9. З.А.Ашуров. Корпоратив бошқарув концепцияси ва моҳияти: илмий назарий ёндашувлар ва уларни ривожлантириш. “Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар” илмий электрон журнали. № 6, ноябрь-декабрь, 2015 йил. http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz/sites/default/files/maqolalar/33_Z_Ashurov.pdf
10. [Pham, H.S.T.](#) and [Nguyen, D.T.](#) (2019), "The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial leverage–profitability relation: Evidence from Vietnam", [Management Research Review](#), Vol. 43 No. 4, pp. 387-409. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-03-2019-0136>
11. Shoeyb Rostamia, Zeynab Rostamib, Samin Kohansal. The Effect of Corporate Governance Components on Return on Assets and Stock Return of Companies Listed in Tehran Stock Exchange. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 36 (2016)137–146.
12. Rizky Fadhillah1, Dian Imanina Burhany. The Mechanism of Corporate Governance, Financial Performance and Corporate Values in Sharia Companies in Indonesia. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Creative Economics, Tourism and Information Management (ICCETIM 2019) - Creativity and Innovation Developments for Global Competitiveness and Sustainability, pages 22-34 ISBN: 978-989-758-451-0
13. Bob Tricker. Corporate governance: principles, policies and practices. – UK.: Oxford university press, 2012. – P. 29-31.
14. Ludo Horsthuis. “Internal corporate governance mechanisms and corporate performance: evidence from dutch listed firms”. http://essay.utwente.nl/79901/1/Horsthuis_MA_BMS.pdf
15. А.Баронов. Теоретические основы корпоративного управления. Экономика и права. №6/2021
16. https://bstudy.net/892413/ekonomika/teoreticheskie_osnovy_korporativnogo_upravleniy_a
17. <https://www.oecd.org/>
18. <https://www.imf.org/en/Home>
19. <https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2022>
20. Author development. Source: <https://www.oecd.org/about/>
21. Управление и корпоративный контроль в акционерном обществе: практ. пособие/ Под ред. Е.П. Губина. — М., 1999. С. 17. Корпоративное право: учебник для вузов/ Под ред. И.С. Шиткиной. — М., 2011. Правовой статус исполнительных органов хозяйственных

- обществ: дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук: 6 .00.03/ Серебрякова А.А. — Ульяновск, 2005. С. 42.
22. Чеботарь Ю.М. ЧЗ4 Корпоративное управление: монография/Чеботарь Ю.М. – М.: Автономная некоммерческая организация «Академия менеджмента и бизнес-администрирования», 2017. – 136 с
23. Хамидулин М.Б. Финансовые механизмы корпоративного управления. Монография. – Т.: Молия, 2008. –204 с.
24. www.researchgate.net/publication/349160150_AKCIADORLIK_ZAMIATLARIDA_KORPORATIV_BOSKARUV_SAMARADORLIGINI_BAOLASNING_METODOLOGIK_ZIATLARI
25. Karimov Z. Distinctive features of the digitization of the corporate management system. Transformation of corporate management models in the context of digitalization of the economy. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/korporativ-bosh-aruv-tizimini-ra-amlashtirish-byicha-ziga-os-hususiyatlar>
26. D. Kh. Suyunov and B. R. Tursunov. Increasing the efficiency of corporate management in joint-stock companies. Central asian academic journal of scientific research. ISSN: 2181-2489 VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 2 | 2022. <file:///C:/Users/admin/Downloads/aktsiyadorlik-zhamiyatlarda-korporativ-bosh-aruv-samaradoligini-oshirish.pdf>